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OUR EXPERIENCE IN THE TREATMENT OF CONGENITAL VAGINAL STRICTURE IN ADOLESCENTS AND YOUNG WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

Every year there is a noticeable increase in the number of adolescents and young women born with genital abnormalities. Genital malformations account for 3–4% of all congenital malformations and are diagnosed in 6.7–25% of patients with disorders in the reproductive system. We examined 26 adolescents and young women with congenital vaginal stricture, aged 18 to 25 years. The complexity of the problem is determined by the difficulty of timely diagnosis and treatment. A large number of diagnostic errors were revealed, which led to incorrect treatment tactics. [2-3]

Doctors of almost all specialties are faced with-- the need to solve specific issues of prevention of violations of the reproductive function of women long before the onset of puberty. Congenital stricture or vaginal stenosis is a complex congenital malformation. [2-3]

Vaginal stenosis does not lead to a delay in the outflow of menstrual blood, but with the onset of sexual activity there are problems of impossibility or difficulty of sexual life. The anomaly is detected late and causes a lot of social problems. In this regard, early detection of congenital abnormalities of the uterus and/or vagina in girls and adolescents, comprehensive treatment and full-fledged medical rehabilitation should in the future contribute to improving women's sexual health.

Key words: congenital disorders, genital organs, vaginal atresia, stricture, adhesive process, girls, diagnostics, vaginoplasty

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НАШ ОПЫТ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ВРОЖДЕННОЙ СТРИКТУРЫ ВЛАГАЛИЩА У ПОДРОСТКОВ И МОЛОДЫХ ЖЕНЩИН

АННОТАЦИЯ

С каждым годом наблюдается заметный рост числа подростков и молодых женщин родившихся с аномалиями развития половых органов. Пороки развития гениталий, составляют 3–4 % всех врожденных пороков и диагностируются у 6,7–25 % пациенток с нарушениями в репродуктивной системе [1].

Нами обследовано 26 подростков и молодых женщин, с врожденной стриктурой влагалища, в возрасте от 18 до 25 лет. Сложность проблемы определяется трудностью своевременной диагностики и лечения. Выявлено большое количество диагностических ошибок, которое привело к неправильной лечебной тактике.

Врачи практически всех специальностей сталкиваются с необходимостью решать специфические вопросы профилактики нарушений репродуктивной функции женщин задолго до наступления периода половой зрелости. Врожденная стриктура или стеноз влагалища является сложным врожденным пороком развития [2-3].

Стеноз влагалища не приводит к задержке оттока менструальной крови, но с началом половой жизни возникают проблемы невозможности или затрудненности половой жизни. Аномалия выявляется поздно и причиняет множество проблем социального характера. В этой связи раннее выявление врожденных аномалий развития матки и/или влагалища у девочек и подростков, комплексное лечение и полноценная медицинская реабилитация должны в перспективе способствовать улучшению сексуального здоровья женщин. [4,5].

Ключевые слова: врожденные нарушения, половые органы, атрезия влагалища, стриктура, спаечный процесс, девочки, диагностика, вагинопластика.

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O'SMIRLAR VA YOSH AYOLLARDA TUG'MA VAGINAL TORAYISHNI DAVOLASH BO'YICHA TAJRIBAMIZ

ANNOTATSIYA

Har yili jinsiy a'zolar rivojlanishida anomaliyalar bilan tug'ilgan o'smirlar va yosh ayollar soni sezilarli darajada oshdi. Jinsiy organlarning malformatsiyasi, barcha tug'ma nuqsonlarning 3-4 foizini tashkil qiladi va reproduktiv tizimi buzilgan bemorlarning 6,7–25 foizida tashxis qilinadi [1].

Biz 18 yoshdan 25 yoshgacha bo'lgan tug'ma vaginal torayishdan 26 nafar o'smir va yosh ayollarni tekshirdik. Muammoning murakkabligi o'z vaqtida tashxis qo'yish va davolash qiyinligi bilan belgilanadi. Noto'g'ri davolash taktikasiga olib kelgan ko'plab diagnostik xatolar aniqlandi.

Deyarli barcha mutaxassisliklar shifokorlari balog'at yoshidan ancha oldin ayollarning reproduktiv funktsiyalari buzilishining oldini olishning o'ziga xos masalalarini hal qilish zarurligiga duch kelishadi. Tug'ma striktura yoki vaginal stenoza murakkab tug'ma nuqsondir [2-3].

Vaginal stenoza hayz ko'rish qonining kechikishiga olib kelmaydi, ammo jinsiy faoliyatning boshlanishi bilan jinsiy faoliyatning mumkin emasligi yoki qiyinligi muammolari paydo bo'ladi. Anomaliya kech aniqlanadi va ko'plab ijtimoiy muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Shu munosabat bilan, qizlar va o'spirinlarda bachadon va/yoki qin rivojlanishidagi tug'ma anomalliklarni erta aniqlash, kompleks davolash va to'liq tibbiy rehabilitatsiya kelajakda ayollarning jinsiy salomatligini yaxshilashga yordam berishi kerak. [4,5].

Kalit so'zlar: tug'ma kasalliklar, jinsiy a'zolar, qin atreziyasi, striktura, yopishqoqlik, qizlar, diagnostika, vaginoplastika.

Congenital malformations - persistent intrauterine abnormalities are caused by one of three reasons: underdevelopment, violation of recanalization or incomplete fusion of the Muller ducts.

Violations of the embryogenesis process at any stage up to the 20th week of gestation lead to the development of a wide variety of uterine and vaginal defects.

In this article, the congenital stricture of the vagina is considered as an example. Stenosis (Greek: Narrow, tight) or stricture (Latin: Stricture - compression) is a congenital or acquired persistent narrowing of the lumen of any hollow anatomical structure of the body. [6-8]

The aim of the study was to analyze errors and improve the management of patients with congenital vaginal stricture.

Materials and methods. To achieve this goal, we conducted a clinical and laboratory analysis of 26 patients with congenital vaginal stricture who applied to the gynecological department of the maternity complex No. 3 and the private clinic "Doctor Shifo Baxt" in Samarkand. All the examined patients and their parents have a carefully collected anamnesis. The average age ranged from 18 to 25 years. The patients were examined only after receiving the voluntary informed consent of the patients and their legal representatives.

Of the total number of examined adolescent patients, there were 19.7%, women of early and active reproductive age, 80.3% of patients. The age of sexual initiation in 71.8% of women ranged from 18 to 25 years.

All patients underwent clinical and laboratory studies, including anamnestic data, general and gynecological examination with an assessment of the features of the structure of the perineum, external genitalia and urethra. Ultrasound examination was performed to clarify the anatomical, topographic and structural features of the internal genitalia. And it was also recommended to perform a vaginoscopy (which was not performed), in case of suspicion of a developmental anomaly with a normally formed vagina, allowing visualization of the lower genital tract. It should be noted that magnetic resonance imaging with a targeted assessment of uterine rudiments is the most reliable diagnostic method of research. [9]

Results: During the treatment, patients complained of the impossibility of sexual intercourse in 26.7% of cases, difficulty in sexual contact in 38% of patients, as well as cyclic pains in the lower abdomen and lower back were noted in 66.1% of patients, fecal and stool incontinence in 12.6% of patients.

The uncertainty of the anatomical boundaries between the "third" vaginas, which makes it difficult to choose the technique of surgery, served as the basis for our thorough study of the structure of the vagina,

the degree of mobility of tissues in relation to the pelvic base, rectum, bladder.

When analyzing patients with vaginal stricture, we encountered diagnostic problems in some atypical cases. In cases of discrepancy between the anamnesis data, the clinical picture and the ultrasound results, magnetic resonance imaging was performed. In the absence of hematocolpos, vaginoscopy turned out to be the most informative, compared with ultrasound and MRI, since this method allowed us to estimate the length of the septum. Careful study of anatomical and topographic features and diagnostics in the preoperative period in patients contributed to the choice of optimal surgical treatment.

The most optimal approach to the treatment of congenital stricture of the vagina is plastic surgery with local tissues by the "W" method of plastic surgery. The operation should allow to avoid restenosis, scarring, to ensure adequate sexual function without the formation of dyspareunia. The advantages of "W" plastic surgery should also include a reduction in injury, complexity and risk of surgery.

Here is an example from practice: Patient I.D., 24 years old, upon admission to the hospital, after a thorough examination, a diagnosis was made: An anomaly of the development of the genitals. Congenital stenosis (stricture) of the middle third of the vagina. Concomitant D.Z the patient underwent surgery - Excision of the stenosing area of the lower third of the vagina. "W" plastic.

Fig. Operation: excision of the stenosing area of the middle third of the vagina. "W" plastic.

After surgery, the patient managed to restore the normal patency of the vagina. There were no complications in the immediate postoperative period. In the long - term period, the patient notes

Conclusion: Thus, vaginal malformations (congenital stricture of the vagina) in girls at any age requires a mandatory examination by a pediatric gynecologist. In order to clarify the nature of the malformation and to resolve the issue of the possibility, as well as the scope of medical care, it is mandatory to perform a comprehensive diagnostic search. If an anomaly of the development of the genitals is detected, in addition to

a standard gynecological examination, vaginoscopy should be performed, and before surgery, an MRI should be performed to assess the anatomical and topographic features of the pelvic organs. The surgical correction of congenital stricture of the vagina is based on the use of local tissues, which is a rational method of treatment that allows to achieve normal patency of the vagina. To assess the condition of patients in the postoperative period, a very important stage is long-term follow-up and rehabilitation with a mandatory assessment of long-term results.

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